

Teachers' Coaching-Based Leadership and Work Engagement as Mediated By Collaborative Attitude

Gretchell D. Barrot¹, Edilberto Z. Andal²

¹Tagbakin Elementary School, Tiaong, Quezon, Philippines 4325

²Laguna State Polytechnic University – San Pablo City Campus, San Pablo City, Philippines 4000

ABSTRACT: This study aimed to explore the mediating role of collaborative attitude of teachers between coaching-based leadership and work engagement in the context of public elementary school setting. Using a descriptive research design, 203 teaching staff responded to a survey questionnaire, which served as the main instrument of the study. The data gathered were subjected to descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation, and inferential statistical analysis, such as Pearson Correlation and Process Macro for mediation. This study revealed that coaching-based leadership were highly practiced among the teachers in all dimensions, including working alliance, open communication, learning and development, and progress and result. Secondly, the engagement of teachers-respondents toward work in physical, emotional, and cognitive was practiced. Thirdly, the respondents observed highly practiced of collaborative attitude. Furthermore, it was found out that the collaborative attitude partially mediates the relationship between coaching-based leadership and work engagement. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. With this, the researcher recommends that aside from utilizing coaching-based leadership strategies, collaborative attitude play a vital role in developing and enhancing work engagement among the teachers.

KEYWORDS: coaching-based leadership, collaborative attitude and work engagement

INTRODUCTION

Most people agree that after entering the field of education, educators need more practice, support, knowledge, and skills. The obligation of teachers today is intense. The environment requires them to compromise with multitude of assurance from students, parents, principals, and the community.

According to Josefina 2021, Coaching-Based Leadership or CBL is becoming increasingly popular in organizations because of its potential benefit for employees' development, well-being, and performance. Also referred to as leader as a coach or managerial coaching (Milner, Mc Carthy, & Milnen, 2018; Pousa, Richards & Trepanver, 2018) one has gained considerable attention as a critical indicator of effective managerial behavior to influence employees without depending on formal authority.

Creating an understanding of teachers' engagement at work is essential. According to Christian et.al (2011), work engagement is a concept of motivation that describes the voluntary allocation of personal resources toward the degree of effort required by a specific vocational function.

Collaborative teachers can improve their work performance by sharing ideas and instructional strategies with one another. To encourage deep team learning, educators collaborate in groups using a continuous cycle of inquiry and reflection (DuFour, 2004, 2007; Hughes & Kristonis, 2008). One of the factors that influence teachers' performance is when they feel engaged with their work which makes them excited, proud, and completely immerse themselves in their work both physically and emotionally.

An organization needs motivated employees who are committed to stay and work toward its' objectives in order to succeed. In this study, the researcher would want to know the teachers' coaching-based leadership and work engagement as mediated by collaborative attitude.

In promoting the teaching-learning process, teachers are the most valuable persons in the education system because they serve as keystones to employ and strengthen the concepts and the system itself to be administered.

Smith (2001), collaboration is much more than physically gathering together for issue discussion or sharing information among team participants, although each component is important in teamwork. Collaborative teams assume ownership of the process and results when participants are encouraged and empowered to work together toward a common goal and reciprocally receive the team achievement (Zurita and Nussbaum, 2004); that is, team achievement highly relies on team members' involvement, attitude, and commitment regarding interacting with each other.

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According to Cox et al. (2010), coaching leaders support and challenge employees to help them maximize their talents and achieve individual development goals. Coaching skills are essential leadership behaviors that help organizations create a competitive advantage (Lee, Idris, & Tuckey, 2019).

The researcher found that collaboration plays an important role in creating harmonious relationships to be engaged in work. It can complete assignments in allotted time and generate an excellent academic result. The collaboration of ideas resulted from effective leadership, especially coaching-based leadership, which empowers people to increase their engagement at work.

In the researcher's workplace, it was evidently observed that when the teachers practiced coaching-based leadership when each of them collaborated, guided and supported each other in a particular task or activity it would result in being more engaged and actively involved. Moreover, the collaborative attitude of the teachers has a great impact and it will benefit most importantly the teaching and learning process.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study determined the teachers' coaching-based leadership and work engagement as mediated by collaborative attitude. The study described the respondents' perception on coaching-based leadership in terms of working alliance, open communication, learning and development, and progress and result. Second, it determined the engagement of teacher-respondents toward work in public elementary school as to physical engagement, emotional engagement and cognitive engagement. Third, it determined the extent of collaborative attitude of the teachers be described.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive correlational method to determine the teachers' coaching-based leadership and work engagement as mediated by their collaborative attitude of Tiaong II District, Division of Quezon.

The descriptive survey is an approach appropriate in determining the characteristics of the research population such as identifying the population's style or performance through interviews or questionnaires in order to distinguish to what extent is the characteristic that the population possessed can be described based on their perceptions or concrete evidences.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were composed of 203 elementary school teachers in Tiaong II District. The entire population of teachers in Tiaong II District were considered as respondent. No sampling technique was applied since all teachers were included.

Research Instrument

This study used a likert scale, the respondents of the study were asked to choose their responses from the given choices. The researcher sent the link of the questionnaire to all schools of Tiaong II to give the teachers all the questionnaire through their school heads. The researcher's adviser was consulted regarding the research questions.

Part I of the questionnaire covered the respondent's profile, which they needed to fill out and check the options that corresponded to their answer. This part includes the respondent's name (optional), the school where they currently teach, gender, age, civil status, highest educational attainment, length of service, and present position.

Part II of the questionnaire was adapted from various studies. It was a list of statements written in a descriptive manner wherein they will rate each based on their perception on coaching-based leadership in terms of working alliance, open communication, learning and development, and progress and result. There were 19 items in this section of the questionnaire, and each statement was given a 5-point Likert scale score that represented the respondents' degree of agreement.

Part III of the questionnaire was also adapted from various studies. It was a list of statements written in a descriptive manner wherein they will rate each based on their perception on their engagement toward work in terms of physical engagement, emotional engagement, and cognitive engagement. This part of the questionnaire had a total of 16 statements that were scored on a 5-point Likert scale, indicating the strength of the respondents' agreement.

Part IV of the questionnaire was also adapted from various studies. It was a list of statements written in a descriptive manner wherein they will rate each based on their perception on collaborative attitude. This part of the questionnaire had a total of 15 statements that were scored on a 5-point Likert scale indicating the strength of the respondents' agreement.

Statistical Treatment

The following tools were used for statistical analyses. The completion of this study relied on the questionnaire, which was used to answer the research problems.

Frequency, percentage, and standard deviation from the mean as a measure of variability were applied to determine the homogeneity of responses on collaborative attitude, coaching-based leadership and work engagement.

Pearson-Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the relationship between the independent and dependent variables of the study at 0.01 level of significance.

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Process Macro for Mediation Analysis was also used to test if the collaborative attitude mediates the relationship between coaching-based leadership and work engagement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tabulated data and the results of the study were presented, the corresponding analysis as well as the interpretation of the data as a result of the statistical treatment used.

Table 1. Coaching-Based Leadership in terms of Working Alliance

INDICATORS <i>As a teacher, I...</i>	MEAN	SD	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
1. have mutual respect for one another.	4.79	0.53	highly practiced
2. truly care about other employees	4.74	0.55	highly practiced
3. feel a sense of commitment.	4.74	0.55	highly practiced
4. works toward mutually agreed upon goals.	4.74	0.55	highly practiced
5. agree on what is important to work on.	4.79	0.53	highly practiced
OVERALL	4.76	0.49	highly practiced

Legend: 4.50 to 5.00 – highly practiced; 3.50 to 4.49 – practiced; 2.50 to 3.49 – moderately practiced; 1.50 to 2.49 – somewhat practiced; 1.00-1.49 – not at all practiced

Table 1 shows the teachers' mean perception of the coaching-based leadership in terms of working alliance. The result revealed an overall mean of 4.76 interpreted as highly practiced. The respondents have mutual respect for one another and agree on what is important to work on as the highest mean indicator. This shows that the respondents practiced this attribute that is essential to develop partnership and build a warm, friendly and caring relationship with other employees.

Demonstrating a real interest in the well-being and future of employees, acting with honesty, setting clear expectations, and fulfilling commitments are all necessary for effective coaching. Because of this, the leader and the workforce have a common meaning, goal, and dedication, which enables high levels of reciprocal engagement to create opportunities and improve performance (Josefina, 2021).

Table 2. Coaching-Based Leadership in terms of Open Communication

INDICATORS <i>As a teacher, I...</i>	MEAN	SD	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
1. ask questions that help to better understand situations, identify causes, and see possible actions for improvement.	4.66	0.57	highly practiced
2. pay close attention when someone is talking.	4.69	0.56	highly practiced
3. listen patiently when someone tell about his/her problems.	4.73	0.55	highly practiced
4. try to be caring in difficult time.	4.69	0.56	highly practiced
5. enable to share feelings.	4.57	0.60	highly practiced
OVERALL	4.67	0.50	highly practiced

Legend: 4.50 to 5.00 – highly practiced; 3.50 to 4.49 – practiced; 2.50 to 3.49 – moderately practiced; 1.50 to 2.49 – somewhat practiced; 1.00-1.49 – not at all practiced

Table 2 presents the teachers' mean perception on the coaching-based leadership in terms of open communication. With its overall mean of 4.67, the respondents agreed that coaching-based leadership is a highly practiced in terms of open communication. The data reveal that coaching-based leadership is highly practiced when teacher listens patiently when someone tell about his/her problems, with the highest mean of 4.73.

One of the most important elements in successful coaching is seen to be open communication (Park et al., 2008). According to Gilley et al. (2010), this dimension relates to the application of successful communication strategies to build rapport with staff members and support their performance and personal and professional potential. In order to foster a deep and meaningful relationship, workers must listen, hear, and act compassionately toward their coworkers in a way that reduces the sway of their individual experiences and viewpoints and fosters a deeper understanding (Kemp, 2009).

Furthermore, it is possible to create an atmosphere where workers feel free to communicate their thoughts and feelings when there is a sufficient degree of acceptance, empathy, understanding, and compassion (Graham et al., 1994; Kemp, 2009).

Table 3. Coaching-Based Leadership in terms of Learning and Development

INDICATORS <i>As a teacher, I...</i>	MEAN	SD	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
1. have main responsibility in employee's learning and development.	4.63	0.55	highly practiced
2. actively provide opportunities to take more responsibility in work.	4.60	0.54	highly practiced
3. constantly provide feedback in order to improve performance.	4.53	0.57	highly practiced

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4. find it easy to identify strengths.	4.40	0.62	practiced
5. appreciate perceptions about strengths because it may help to do work better.	4.56	0.58	highly practiced
OVERALL	4.54	0.51	highly practiced

Legend: 4.50 to 5.00 – highly practiced; 3.50 to 4.49 – practiced; 2.50 to 3.49 – moderately practiced; 1.50 to 2.49 – somewhat practiced; 1.00-1.49 – not at all practiced

Presented in Table 3 is the mean perception on coaching-based leadership in terms of learning and development. With an overall mean of 4.54, the respondents agreed that coaching-based leadership is highly practiced in terms of learning and development. The respondents have main responsibility in employee's learning and development with the highest mean of 4.63.

According to Karlsen and Berg (2020), coaching leaders are more successful when they give employees constructive criticism and assist them in recognizing, developing, and utilizing their own abilities. By encouraging workers to take on new challenges and think back on their past experiences, coaching leaders directly promote learning and development. According to Schaufeli and Taris (2014), people who receive coaching from their leaders are more likely to stay involved with their work and acquire knowledge about how to achieve their objectives (Heslin et al., 2006). Utilizing their strengths at work increases employee engagement (Harter, Schmidt, & Hayes, 2002) and increases goal success (Linley, Nielsen, Gillett, & Biswas-Diener, 2010).

Table 4. Coaching-Based Leadership in terms of Progress and Result

INDICATORS As a teacher, I...	MEAN	SD	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
1. set objectives which are ambitious but achievable.	4.43	0.61	practiced
2. am very good at helping employees to develop clear, simple, and achievable action plans.	4.43	0.56	practiced
3. always ask about the progress on their objectives.	4.39	0.60	practiced
4. adequately follow up and evaluates my progress toward my goals.	4.42	0.57	practiced
OVERALL	4.42	0.51	practiced

Legend: 4.50 to 5.00 – highly practiced; 3.50 to 4.49 – practiced; 2.50 to 3.49 – moderately practiced; 1.50 to 2.49 – somewhat practiced; 1.00-1.49 – not at all practiced

Table 4 shows the teachers' mean perception on the coaching-based leadership in terms of progress and result. The result revealed an overall mean of 4.42 interpreted as practiced. The respondents set objectives which are ambitious but achievable and very good in helping employees to develop clear, simple, and achievable action plans both revealed with the highest mean indicators of 4.43. Coaching leaders and managers work collaboratively with each employee to set challenging development goals that motivate performance (Dahling et al., 2016). According to Grant & Cavanagh (2007), they help employees to monitor and evaluate their progress and manage both responsibilities in the process to make consistent progress.

Table 5. Summary of Respondents' Perception on the Coaching-Based Leadership

COACHING-BASED LEADERSHIP	MEAN	SD	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
Working Alliance	4.76	0.49	highly practiced
Open Communication	4.67	0.50	highly practiced
Learning and Development	4.54	0.51	highly practiced
Progress and Result	4.42	0.51	practiced
OVERALL	4.60	0.50	highly practiced

Legend: 4.50 to 5.00 – highly practiced; 3.50 to 4.49 – practiced; 2.50 to 3.49 – moderately practiced; 1.50 to 2.49 – somewhat practiced; 1.00-1.49 – not at all practiced

Presented in Table 5 is the summary of respondents' perception on Coaching-Based Leadership in terms of Working Alliance, Open Communication, Learning and Development, and Progress and Result. The result revealed an overall mean of 4.60 with verbal interpretation of highly practiced.

Among coaching-based leadership contributing factors, working alliance got the highest mean of 4.76 which is interpreted as highly practiced. Coach-client working alliance is characterized by mutual agreement on goals to achieve during the coaching, on tasks that facilitate goal attainment, and on a bonding partnership. Moreover, daily interactions, along with specific leader coaching skills, such as open communication with employees, encourage employees to perform extra-role behaviors in the organization (Raza, Ali, Ahmed, & Ahmad, 2018). Coaching leaders directly foster learning and development by encouraging employees to try new opportunities and reflect on their experiences.

In term of Progress and Result, it is interpreted as practiced. It is a good leader's trait which everyone in a team particularly school setting is actively involved in planning, decision-making and liable to its' result. Dahl & Molly 2006 state that coaching-based

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leadership arises when coaching is the organization's primary method of management and collaboration. Therefore, the most fundamental way to improve employee performance is for them to actively engage in their own learning.

Because of their regular interactions and close proximity to employees, leaders acting as coaches have a higher impact on employee attitudes (Theeboom et al., 2014). These one-on-one conversations help employees learn to self-regulate their behavior, which boosts motivation and helps them develop their abilities and personal qualities (Berg & Karlsen, 2016). By encouraging workers to take on new challenges and think back on their past experiences, coaching leaders directly promote learning and development. According to Schaufeli and Taris (2014), people who receive coaching from their peers are more likely to stay involved with their work and acquire knowledge about how to achieve their objectives (Heslin et al., 2006).

Table 6. Physical Engagement of the Teacher-Respondents toward Work in Public Elementary School

INDICATORS As a teacher, I...	MEAN	SD	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
1. feel bursting with energy.	4.25	0.60	practiced
2. feel strong and vigorous.	4.32	0.61	practiced
3. feel like going to work when I get up in the morning.	4.41	0.61	practiced
4. can continue working for very long periods at a time.	4.26	0.67	practiced
5. am very resilient mentally.	4.33	0.60	practiced
6. always persevere even when things do not go well.	4.33	0.61	practiced
OVERALL	4.32	0.51	practiced

Legend: 4.50 to 5.00 – highly practiced; 3.50 to 4.49 – practiced; 2.50 to 3.49 – moderately practiced; 1.50 to 2.49 – somewhat practiced; 1.00-1.49 – not at all practiced

Table 6 reveals that all statements in physical engagement of teacher-respondents toward work are practiced with 4.32 as its overall mean. The result implies that the teachers were physically engaged toward their work specifically in teaching-learning process. The teachers-respondents feel like going to work when they get up every morning which got the highest mean of 4.41 interpreted as practiced.

Physical engagement refers to the intensity or frequency of one's energy and effort expenditures during work in addition to the quantity of energy expended. An employee is considered to have the vigor to perform when they exhibit high levels of energy and mental clarity. High levels of energy and mental fortitude when working, the willingness to put effort into one's work, and perseverance in the face of adversity are characteristics of it. The teachers practiced physical engagement toward work in which they feel strong, always persevere, resilient, energetic and continue to work even in their difficult times.

Table 7. Emotional Engagement of the Teacher-Respondents toward Work in Public Elementary School

INDICATORS As a teacher, I...	MEAN	SD	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
1. find the work that I do full of meaning and purpose.	4.46	0.61	practiced
2. am enthusiastic about teaching.	4.46	0.60	practiced
3. consider my job inspires me.	4.47	0.60	practiced
4. am proud of the work that I do.	4.58	0.56	highly practiced
5. find my job challenging.	4.57	0.55	highly practiced
OVERALL	4.51	0.51	highly practiced

Legend: 4.50 to 5.00 – highly practiced; 3.50 to 4.49 – practiced; 2.50 to 3.49 – moderately practiced; 1.50 to 2.49 – somewhat practiced; 1.00-1.49 – not at all practiced

Presented in Table 7 is the emotional engagement of the teacher-respondents toward work. The result revealed an overall mean of 4.51 interpreted as highly practiced. Statements 1, 2, and 3 falls under practiced while statements 4 and 5 are highly practiced. The respondents proud of the work that they do as the highest mean of 4.58 interpreted as highly practiced. The result implies that the teachers were emotionally engaged toward their work.

Generally, people who are emotionally work engaged would feel good or happy about their work, and experiencing such positive effect would give them pleasant feelings about their work. Dedication to one's work equates to emotional engagement. Job devotion is the foundation for employee motivation to perform well, and it can inspire workers to take deliberate actions to further the organization's goals. Teachers who are passionate, proud of what they do, willing to take on new challenges, and who feel that their work has meaning and purpose are the ones who are most dedicated to their jobs.

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Table 8. Cognitive Engagement of the Teacher-Respondents toward Work in Public Elementary School

INDICATORS <i>As a teacher, I...</i>	MEAN	SD	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
1. pay a lot of attention to my work.	4.56	0.55	highly practiced
2. really "throw" myself into my work.	4.30	0.64	practiced
3. work with intensity.	4.35	0.62	practiced
4. try my hardest to perform well while teaching.	4.50	0.59	highly practiced
5. forget everything else around me when I am working.	4.09	0.77	practiced
OVERALL	4.36	0.53	practiced

Legend: 4.50 to 5.00 – highly practiced; 3.50 to 4.49 – practiced; 2.50 to 3.49 – moderately practiced; 1.50 to 2.49 – somewhat practiced; 1.00-1.49 – not at all practiced

Table 8 shows the cognitive engagement of the teacher-respondents toward work. The result revealed an overall mean of 4.36 interpreted as practiced. The respondents pay a lot of attention to their work which got the highest mean of 4.56 interpreted as highly practiced. Therefore, the teachers were cognitively engaged toward related work.

People who are cognitively work engaged would have more positive thoughts about and pay more attention to their work. Furthermore, Thomas (2009) proposed that engaged workers will pay attention to cognitive processing in addition to behaviors, while May et al. (2004) stated that thinking is essential to cognitive job engagement. Since individuals who are engaged in their job are more likely to complete their tasks, absorption can assist organizations in meeting set goals and targets. We can conclude that employee performance is positively impacted by absorption.

Therefore, in order to perform well at work, cognitive work engagement would entail devoting time, focus, thought, and concentration to the task at hand.

Table 9. Summary of Respondents' Engagement toward Work

WORK ENGAGEMENT	MEAN	SD	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
Physical Engagement	4.32	0.51	practiced
Emotional Engagement	4.51	0.51	highly practiced
Cognitive Engagement	4.36	0.53	practiced
OVERALL	4.40	0.52	practiced

Legend: 4.50 to 5.00 – highly practiced; 3.50 to 4.49 – practiced; 2.50 to 3.49 – moderately practiced; 1.50 to 2.49 – somewhat practiced; 1.00-1.49 – not at all practiced

Presented in Table 9 is the summary of respondents' engagement toward work as to physical, emotional, and cognitive. Emotional engagement is highly practiced while Physical and Cognitive both interpreted as practiced with an overall mean of 4.40 interpreted as practiced. Thus, teachers were physically, emotionally, and cognitively engaged toward related work.

The overall conceptual definition of work engagement is defined here as "the intentional involvement with or attachment to tasks, objectives, or organizational activities cognitively, emotionally, and physically, i.e., by having positive thoughts about improving one's effectiveness, feeling positive emotions about executing the tasks, and voluntarily utilizing one's energy and effort to achieve those tasks."

Additionally, an engaged worker should have a high degree of teaching performance and devote a variety of resources—that is, emotional, physical, and cognitive resources—to their task.

Moreover, Kahn (1990) contended that there might be a relationship between performance and the work engagement.

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Table 10. Collaborative Attitude

Indicators		Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
As a teacher, I ...				
1	value other teachers' ideas.	4.58	0.57	highly practiced
2	engage in dialogue with colleagues as to their performance, practice and reflection.	4.58	0.55	highly practiced
3	frequently communicate expectations around school norms, beliefs, values and goals.	4.55	0.56	highly practiced
4	promote professional involvement among other staff.	4.61	0.57	highly practiced
5	trust the professional judgements of other teachers.	4.57	0.58	highly practiced
6	foster professional relationships with other staff.	4.57	0.57	highly practiced
7	share leadership responsibilities with peers.	4.59	0.56	highly practiced
8	provide opportunities and resources for teacher collaboration.	4.58	0.56	highly practiced
9	provide incentives for other teachers' professional learning.	4.43	0.64	practiced
10	promote professional development.	4.57	0.56	highly practiced
11	support risk-taking and innovation in teaching.	4.48	0.59	practiced
12	allow other teachers' opinions and suggestions.	4.64	0.54	highly practiced
13	praise other teachers that perform well.	4.64	0.54	highly practiced
14	involve colleagues in the decision-making process.	4.59	0.58	highly practiced
15	protect instruction and planning time.	4.59	0.56	highly practiced
Overall		4.57	0.48	highly practiced

Legend: 4.50 to 5.00 – highly practiced; 3.50 to 4.49 – practiced; 2.50 to 3.49 – moderately practiced; 1.50 to 2.49 – somewhat practiced; 1.00-1.49 – not at all practiced

Table 10 reveals that the extent of collaborative attitude of the teachers is highly practiced with 4.57 as its overall mean. Therefore, the respondents revealed highly practiced of collaborative attitude.

According to Harvard Business Review, in order to develop strategies and find solutions, collaborative executives routinely seek out a diversity of viewpoints and ideas among their colleagues. Employee engagement, trust, and likelihood of taking ownership of work all increase as a result. Managers and executives may foster an inclusive workplace that stimulates teams, unleashes creativity, and fosters a happy and productive work culture by practicing collaborative leadership.

Effective leadership fosters collaboration, which benefits the entire team or business in many ways. It is reasonable to anticipate the following effects when leaders are perceived as valuing collaboration: Higher levels of employee engagement are frequently correlated with increased productivity. Workers who feel that they are part of a team environment at work rather than just following directives from superiors will be more content and invested in their positions.

Collaborative attitude is used to describe a person or a group that is open to work together in an effort to reach mutual goals. The team displayed a strong collaborative attitude as they worked together to solve the problem.

To summarize, no organization or team can survive without a deep embedded culture of collaboration. That is the secret to success, and we can all build a collaborative environment that will benefit our business objectives as well as our personal growth if we have strong work ethics, trust, and compassion.

Table 11. Relationship Between Coaching-Based Leadership and Collaborative Attitude

COACHING-BASED LEADERSHIP	COLLABORATIVE ATTITUDE
Working Alliance	.497**
Open Communication	.517**
Leadership and Development	.506**
Progress and Result	.491**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

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Based on Table 11, it shows that there is a significant relationship between Coaching-Based Leadership in terms of Working Alliance; Open Communication; Leadership and Development; Progress and Result; and Collaborative Attitude. The results also stated that collaborative attitude in relation to coaching-based leadership in terms of open and communication got a high correlation of 0.517 and interpreted as having a strong correlation.

According to Aguilar 2013, the most thorough and comprehensive study on coaching was done on 2004 by the Annenberg Foundation for Education Reform. The report concludes that effective coaching encourages collaborative, reflective practice. Compared to working alone, coaching enables teachers to use their knowledge more frequently, more profoundly, and more consistently. Through coaching, educators can become more adept at reflecting on and applying what they have learned to their work with students as well as to their work with one another. The goal of collaborative coaching is to support individuals as they grow, change, learn, and eventually become more productive. People will be more effective in their growth and development efforts when they feel that they are a part of the process rather than that changes or answers are being imposed on them in an authoritative or directive manner. It simply refers to collaborating with someone to develop a strategy, plan, or understanding addressing a given circumstance, chance, or conundrum.

Table 12. Relationship Between Collaborative Attitude and Work Engagement

<i>Relationship Between Collaborative Attitude and Work Engagement</i>			
	Work Engagement		
	Physical Engagement	Emotional Engagement	Cognitive Engagement
Collaborative Attitude	.583**	.579**	.614**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Based on Table 12, it shows that there is a significant relationship between Collaborative Attitude and Work Engagement in terms of Physical, Emotional and Cognitive Engagement. However, it is clearly shows that collaborative attitude in relation to work engagement in terms of cognitive engagement got a high correlation of 0.614 and interpreted as having a strong correlation.

Collaborative leaders consider everyone in decision-making, share leaderships to others, and seek out opinions. As a result, employees are more engaged toward related work.

According to Aijazi 2022, engagement and collaboration are inter-related. They can blend into each other and share characteristics. For example, fostering a culture of healthy connections inside your company can help to increase employee engagement and happiness while also fostering stronger teamwork. Establishing solid relationships is essential for laying the groundwork for collaboration.

Table 13. Relationship Between Coaching-Based Leadership and Work Engagement

<i>Relationship Between Coaching-Based Leadership and Work Engagement</i>			
Coaching-Based Leadership	Work Engagement		
	Physical Engagement	Emotional Engagement	Cognitive Engagement
Working Alliance	.437**	.498**	.478**
Open Communication	.464**	.514**	.549**
Learning and Development	.644**	.640**	.646**
Progress and Result	.644**	.608**	.598**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 13 shows the correlation between coaching-based leadership and work engagement. It can be gleaned that all variables under Coaching-Based Leadership specifically Working Alliance, Open Communication, Leadership and Development, Progress and Result registered significant relationships with Work Engagement in terms of Physical, Emotional and Cognitive. However, it is

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notable that among the dimensions in coaching-based leadership; learning and development, and progress and result in relation to work engagement in the dimension of physical engagement got a high correlation of 0.644 respectively and interpreted as having a strong correlation. On the other hand, learning and development under coaching-based leadership in relation to work engagement in the dimension of emotional engagement and cognitive engagement got the highest correlation of 0.640 and 0.646 respectively and also interpreted as having a strong correlation.

A culture of value and hearing is fostered by coaching leaders. This leadership style increases team members' involvement by actively including them in decision-making and problem-solving. Employee retention costs are decreased by engaged staff members who are more dedicated, effective, and likely to stick around. Employee engagement is higher when a leader coaches them because they get greater help from the leader to accomplish their objectives (Kim, 2014).

Table 14. Mediation Analysis of Collaborative Attitude on the Relationship Between Coaching-Based Leadership and Work Engagement

Effect	Estimate	SE	95% Confidence Interval		t	p
			Lower	Upper		
Direct	.4737	.0578	.3597	.5877	8.1943	.0000
Indirect	.2610	.0663	.1265	.3848	3.9367	
Total	.7348	.0540	.6282	.8413	13.5955	.0000

Effect	Estimate	SE	95% Confidence Interval		t	p
			Lower	Upper		
Coaching --> Engagement	.4737	.0578	.3597	.5877	8.1943	.0000
Engagement --> Collab	.4202	.0534	.3149	.5255	7.8679	.0000
Coaching --> Collab	.6212	.0625	.4979	.7446	9.9347	.0000
C --> E --> CL	.2610	.0663	.1265	.3848	3.9367	

Note: partial mediation

Table 14 presents a mediation analysis examining the collaborative attitude of the teachers on the relationship between coaching-based leadership and work engagement. The analysis aims to determine if the extent of collaborative attitude of the teachers mediates the relationship between coaching-based leadership and work engagement of the teachers.

The direct effect represents the relationship between coaching-based leadership and work engagement of the teachers without considering the mediating role of the extent of collaborative attitude. In this analysis, the direct effect estimate is 0.4737 with a 95% confidence interval ranging from 0.3597 to 0.5877. The t-value is 8.1943, and the associated p-value is 0.0000. This implies that coaching-based leadership directly and significantly impacts the teachers' work engagement. This finding highlights the importance of coaching-based leadership. The use of various leadership styles that depends on the school situation can enhance teachers' work engagement.

Furthermore, the indirect effect represents the relationship between coaching-based leadership and work engagement mediated by collaborative attitude of the teachers. In this analysis, the indirect effect estimate is 0.2610 with a 95% confidence interval ranging from 0.1265 to 0.3848. the t-value is 3.9367. This suggests that the extent of collaborative attitude plays a significant role in coaching-based leadership in the enhancement of teachers' work engagement. Manifesting that the collaborative attitude of the teachers by controlling their own level of motivation and behavior will reflect on their coaching-based leadership style. Their confidence on the use of various coaching-based leadership traits can enhance teachers' work engagement on physical, emotional and cognitive aspects.

Based on these results, there is a partial mediation of collaborative attitude of the teachers between the relationship of coaching-based leadership and work engagement.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings as summarized, the following were concluded: First, it can be concluded there is a significant relationship between coaching-based leadership in terms of Working Alliance; Open Communication; Learning and Development; and Progress and Result and collaborative attitude. Thus, the hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between coaching-based leadership and collaborative attitude is rejected. Second, there is a significant relationship between collaborative attitude and work engagement in terms of physical, emotional and cognitive. Thus, the hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship

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between collaborative attitude and work engagement is rejected. Third, there is a significant relationship between coaching-based leadership in terms of Working Alliance; Open Communication; Learning and Development; and Progress and Result and work engagement in physical, emotional, and cognitive. Thus, the hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between coaching-based leadership and work engagement is rejected. Lastly, there is a partial mediation of collaborative attitude of the teachers between the relationship of coaching-based leadership and work engagement. Thus, the hypothesis stating that the collaborative attitude of the teachers does not mediate the relationship between coaching-based leadership and work engagement is rejected. From the drawn conclusion, the following recommendations were formulated: For the school, it may be recommended to promote the continuous practice of coaching-based leadership with collaborative attitude that will enhance engagement toward work. For School administrators, they may consider the result of the extent of their collaborative attitude and practiced coaching-based leadership. Those practices and traits will help the teachers to be much engaged at their work. The school head may be motivated to improve their supervisory skills and practices. For the teachers, the result of the study may help them to become aware of the importance of practicing coaching-based leadership and the holistic engagement toward work. It may also be a way to improve their classroom instruction and management as well as help them meet their professional growth and developmental needs. For the future researchers, findings of the study may serve as basis of information for researchers who are interested on studies related to teachers' coaching-based leadership and work engagement mediated by their collaborative attitude.

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